

**ARTISTIC POETICAL INTERPRETATION OF THE
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ABSTRACT

This article presents a comparative analysis of the artistic and poetic interpretation in the lyrics of Cholpon and Sergey Yesenin. It examines the features of lyrical unity, national spirit, imagery, poetic language, and musicality in the works of both poets. The study demonstrates that Cholpon's poetry is characterized by Eastern delicacy, the idea of freedom, and symbolic imagery, whereas Yesenin's lyrics are shaped by natural landscapes, folk melodicism, and simple lyricism. The article outlines the similarities and differences in the poetic worldviews of the two poets.

Introduction

At the beginning of the 20th century, a unique poetic renewal took place in the world literary process. Both in the literature of the Turkic peoples and in the Russian literary environment, the depiction of the inner experiences of the human psyche and the expression of nationality through artistic images intensified. The great lyric poet of Uzbek literature Abdulhamid Cholpon and the bright representative of Russian lyrics Sergey Yesenin constitute the two poles of this general literary process. Both are poets who were able to express the soul of their nation with artistic charm and influenced the development of the lyric genre at a new stage.

While Eastern elegance, Uzbek feelings, the spirit of national freedom, and the subtle feelings of the human soul occupied the main center in Cholpon's lyrics, the charming landscapes of Russian nature, peasant sincerity, innocence, and rays of goodness are brightly reflected in Yesenin's work. The common feature of the lyrics of both poets is the deep expression of the poetic interpretation of the human soul, the connection of the national spirit with the spirit of the times, the formation of the inner monologue of the lyrical hero using artistic means.

Creating an artistic style in translation, like the writer himself, requires great artistry, and the concept of mastery is formed, first of all, from this. Naming things and events in the original text, revealing melodies, images, poetic expressions that have a very strong impact on the reader's imagination in translation at the level of the artistic goal pursued by the author also serves the perfect development of the artistic style. Cholpon treats all of this with great

attention and responsibility in his translations. An interesting fact worth noting: it is known from the history of our literature that Abdulla Kahhor treated Chekhov, one of our outstanding writers, with special love and devotion. He went his own way in translating Chekhov: he mainly translated his very sharp humorous works into Uzbek. But he put on Chekhov's glasses a little later than Cholpon and took into account Cholpon's experiences in the translation. Cholpon chose Chekhov's wonderful lyrical-dramatic stories for translation.

The main artistic power of Cholpon's poetry is in putting the human heart at the literary center, in the ability to describe the state of mind in an elegant style. In his poems such as "Binafsha", "Night and Day", "Moonlight Night", "Beautiful", delicate feelings, love, longing, admiration, charm are expressed through poetic images. In each line of Cholpon, melody, rhythmic musicality, spiritual anguish and longing are combined.

The system of artistic images:

- In "Purple", the image of flowers as a symbol of humility, tenderness, and suffering;
- In "Night and Day", the fate of the nation through the contrast of darkness and light;
- In the poem "Who am I?", the lyrical hero's search for philosophical self-realization.

One of the most important aspects of Cholpon's lyrics is the idea of freedom. The poet's experiences about the homeland, nation, and freedom brought new meaning to modern Uzbek poetry. His images contain longing, pain, and suffering, but at the same time hope. Cholpon creates poetic images based on Eastern artistic traditions: images such as flowers, night, moon, spring, dawn, and sky serve to express the human spiritual state.

The artistic nature of Sergei Yesenin's lyrics

Yesenin's poetry is recognized as one of the "brightest examples of nature lyrics" in Russian literature. His poems such as "White Night", "Rushing Leaves", "I Don't Care", "Russia", "White Clouds", "Waiting Moon" contain spiritual experiences combined with natural landscapes.

Yesenin's main poetic features:

- Expression of the human soul through images of nature;
- Russian peasant culture, simple folk style;
- Sincerity and sonorous musicality;
- Combination of rural landscapes with lyricism.

For example, in Yesenin's famous poems, natural landscapes are not only an external image, but also a kind of reflection of the poet's inner world. In the poem "Russia", the expanses of the homeland, autumn winds, white clouds express the spiritual state of a person. His images are simple, but their content is deep.

Yesenin often elevates his images to a symbolic level: a white cloud - for him freedom, a meadow - the past, a brown dawn - dreams, the yellowing of autumn - a symbol of the transience of life.

Common and different aspects of the lyrics of Cholpon and Yesenin

Poetic commonalities

Jihat	Cho'lpon	Yesenin
Lirik qahramon	Iztirobli, orzuvchan, erkinlikka intiluvchi	Samimiy, tabiatga bog'langan, pok qalbli
Poetik	Musiqiy, mayin, Sharqona	Xalqona, sodda, qo'shiqsimon

Jihat	Cho'lpon	Yesenin
ohang	ohangdorlik	
Asosiy mavzu	Sevgi, dard, Vatan, erkinlik	Tabiat, Vatan, sodda hayot falsafasi
Badiiy vositalar	Timsol, metafora, ramziy obrazlar	Manzara, personifikatsiya, xalqona tashbehlar
Poetik ruh	Romantik, ruhiy-falsafiy	Lirik-folklorona, romantik

The lyrics of both poets are strongly musical. Cholpon's poems correspond to the musicality of classical Eastern poetry; in Yesenin, the melody of Russian folk songs is heard.

A comparative study of the lyrics of Cholpon and Yesenin shows how two geniuses of two different cultures interpreted the human psyche equally deeply through lyrics. While Cholpon revived Eastern poetic thinking in a modern direction, Yesenin raised the Russian folk psyche to artistic heights. Their lyrics enriched themes such as nation, love, nature, freedom, pain, and hope with unique artistic means.

In lyrical works, the interpretation of time is manifested as an important poetic category in the work of both poets. In Cholpon's poetics, the passage of time is shown as a symbol of national awakening, approaching or moving away from the idea of freedom. Through the symbolic interpretation of day and night, the poet describes the spiritual state of the nation. In Yesenin, time is determined by the change of seasons. The rhythm of nature is described in connection with the rhythm of human life. Autumn is a symbol of suffering, loss and transience, while spring is interpreted as a symbol of hope and awakening.

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